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Removal of Per- and Poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and Pharmaceuticals onto Activated Carbon from Wastewater Effluents

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent chemicals. Their toxicity and bioaccumulation make them harmful. High exposure to these compounds increases the risk of dangerous health problems for human beings [1]. In addition, pharmaceutical micropollutants are contaminants of emerging concern because they are continuously released into the environment [2]. This poses a long-term problem for human health and the environment. Activated carbons (AC) prepared from biomass waste are efficient and versatile biomaterials for removing contaminants. In order to implement adsorption processes on an industrial scale, this study involved the selection of 3 PFAS (perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS) and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA)) and 3 pharmaceuticals (diclofenac (DCF), valsartan (VAL) and iopromide (IOP)) to evaluate their performance on fixed-bed columns using a biomaterials / activated carbons (ACs) synthesized from biomass waste. The adsorption processes of these systems and their breakthrough curves were determined. The experimental results were compared to a commercially available activated carbon, NORIT demonstrating the best performance of these novel biomaterials. Synthetic water matrices and real water samples from a wastewater treatment plant effluent were used in the experiments. This work contributes to the removal of very important contaminants of emerging concern.

Figure 1. Fixed bed column used for PFAS and pharmaceuticals breakthrough tests.

References

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